

Bias in Numbers Part 2: The Multiplicative Inverse of 0, Mathematical Indeterminacy and the Infinite Cake

By Allan Porter

“Arithmetic is like an ocean. Many swim freely on the surface never realizing or appreciating its depth. However to divers, there are worlds and worlds to explore beneath.”

Introduction

It has been said that any number divided by 0 essentially “breaks” arithmetic and returns an undefined or indeterminate value. However, what does it actually mean for a number to be undefined or indeterminate? Isn't a number just a measure of quantity? How can there ever be an undefined or indeterminate quantity? Furthermore, if 0 is a real number on the number line then shouldn't it be treated the same as any other number in terms of it being “dividable”?

The Multiplicative Inverse of 0

One of the main reasons why division by zero is not allowed in contemporary arithmetic is because it leads to paradoxes. One example of such a paradox occurs when attempting to find the multiplicative inverse of 0. For reference, a *multiplicative inverse* is the number that it takes to multiply any number by in order to return a value of 1. An example of this would be how the multiplicative inverse of 4 is $1/4$. For in order to get from a quantity of 4 to a quantity of 1, one must essentially instantiate 4 ($1/4$) times in order to only get the quantity of a single one of the 4's whole number components.

However, what is the multiplicative inverse of 0? If $1/4$ instantiations of 4 are needed to return 1, then how many instantiations of 0 would it take to return 1? Intuitively, there should be no answer. Surely, 0 added to 0 any number of times should still essentially return a quantity of 0. For if one kept placing 0 oranges in a bin, said bin would never actually have any oranges inside of it. Therefore, regardless of the number of 0's there are added together the result should still be the same and never equal to 1. However, does this really make sense? If 0 is really a real number on the number line, then shouldn't it have a multiplicative inverse just like every other number both positive and negative? Why is 0 so special among them?

The Paradox

Now suppose that a real number “X” is thought up and defined only by its ability to be multiplied by 0 and return 1.

Using this logic it can be said that:

$$X \cdot 0 = 1$$

However, it is known that any real number multiplied by 0 must equal 0 since 0 instantiations of any quantity, no matter the quantity always results in a total quantity of 0.

Therefore employing this axiom:

$X \cdot 0$ would also need to equal 0 at the same time it equals 1

This would imply that $X \cdot 0 =$ both 1 and 0, further implying that $1=0$. On the surface, since 1 does not equal 0 it must be that such a number X does not exist as a multiplicative inverse of 0 unless it has properties that are completely undefined by contemporary mathematics, where if instantiated 0 times it doesn't equal 0.

Therefore, at this point there are essentially 2 options: 1) Conclude that 0 has no multiplicative inverse or 2) Assume that 0 does have a multiplicative inverse but this multiplicative inverse has vastly different properties than any other real number and therefore doesn't follow the normal rules of commutation that define $X \cdot 0$ as always 0.

Finding Such a Number

Now assume that choice 2 is correct and there does exist such a number X that multiplied by 0 equals 1. How could such a number ever be found? One way to do this would be to generalize a multiplicative inverse function as it exists for all other numbers and then assign it to 0 to see what number it would return:

Therefore:

If the Multiplicative Inverse of 5 is $1/5$ (since $5 \cdot 1/5 = 1$)

And

If the Multiplicative Inverse of 4 is $1/4$ (since $4 \cdot 1/4 = 1$)

And

If the Multiplicative Inverse of 3 is $1/3$ (since $3 \cdot 1/3 = 1$)

And

If the Multiplicative Inverse of 2 is $1/2$ (since $2 \cdot 1/2 = 1$)

And

If the Multiplicative Inverse of 1 is $1/1$ (since $1 \cdot 1/1 = 1$)

Then a function could be generalized where the Multiplicative Inverse of a number n is simply:

$1/n$ (since $n \cdot 1/n = 1$).

Intuitively this makes sense as it is simply a generalized way to show that any quantity divided by itself equals 1. For since division is the inverse of multiplication, this can simply be written as $n/n = n \cdot (1/n)$ which then solving for 1 equals $1/n \cdot n$. This makes sense as any quantity n divided into n piles would always result in there being 1 quantity per pile.

Now if this function $n \cdot 1/n = 1$ were to be applied to 0, then its multiplicative inverse would need to be $1/0$ which tends to infinity.

Therefore, using this logic:

$$0 * (1/0) = 1$$

And

$$x = 1/0 \text{ or } \infty$$

Now using $1/0$ as the multiplicative inverse should work in that:

1. It's arithmetic alone makes intuitive sense as $1 = (1/0) * 0$ can be re-constructed as $1/0 = 1/0$ which should be true.

2. $1/0$ as the multiplicative inverse of 0 follows the same generalization function of multiplicative inverse as do all other numbers. This therefore re-establishes 0 as having the same properties as all other real numbers which it intuitively should.

However, is it really this simple? Does it really make sense to overturn a rule so fundamental as the "no division by 0 rule" in contemporary arithmetics just to give 0 a multiplicative inverse? To answer these questions there are a number of potential pitfalls with this generalization of the multiplicative inverse function to 0 that need to be addressed first:

Pitfall #1: The Generalization $0 * (1/0) = 1$ implies that $0/0 = 1$

One issue with applying the $(1/n)$ generalization to $n = 0$ is that implies that $0/0 = 1$. The reason that it would imply such an equality is because:

$$\text{If } 0 * (1/0) = 1$$

Then substituting $0/1$ for 0 (as 0 is the same as 0 divided by 1) yields:

$$(0 / 1) * (1 / 0) = 1$$

Solving for the inside of each of the parentheses would return:

$$0/0 = 1$$

Therefore, if $0 * (1/0) = 1$, this implies that $0/0 = 1$. However, can $0/0 = 1$ actually make sense?

What $0/0$ essentially means is that 0 quantity is being divided into 0 piles. Therefore, this can be akin to 0 quantity never actually being divided into any piles at all. However, wouldn't this simply return the same quantity of 0? For if the 0 quantity never was actually divided into any "piles" in the first place shouldn't that essentially still mean that there exists a total of 0 quantity? How can such a quantity ever be equal to 1?

Pitfall # 2: Paradoxes

Besides for the implication of $0/0 = 1$, one other problem with $0*(1/0)$ being set as equal to 1 is that division by 0 in this case leads to paradoxes. For if $1/0 = \infty$ and $0 * \infty = 1$, then one could also argue that $0 * \infty = 2$ since $2/0$ would $= \infty$. This is because if there exists a number x such that $x*0 = 1$, then shouldn't there also exist a number y that $y*0 = 2$? For if such a number x would be $1/0$ which tends to infinity then shouldn't y be $2/0$ which also tends to infinity? For if there are an infinite number of 0's required to equal to 1 then surely there would also be at least an infinite number of 0's required to equal to 2!

Furthermore, according to this logic $0 * \infty$ could essentially equal any real positive number since it will take at least ∞ 0's in order to add up to said number. Therefore, allowing division by 0 inevitably leads to paradoxes.

Pitfall # 3: Is $0 * (1/0) = 1$ Actually Intuitive On a Non-Arithmetic Level? Furthermore, Isn't Division By Zero not even allowed?

Finally, even when not factoring in paradoxes or the intuition of $0/0=1$, this idea that $(1/0)$ 0's can ever equal any value other than 0 let alone 1 sounds very counterintuitive. For if $0+0$ is always equal to 0 then shouldn't it not matter how many $(0+0)$'s there are; shouldn't $0+0+0\dots$ always need to equal 0 no matter the number of 0's? Arithmetically, this statement should be true as division by zero is not allowed in arithmetic - essentially rendering $(1/0)$ as being "disallowed" to be included in any equation.

However, even if division by 0 is allowed, $0*(1/0) = 1$ is still extremely counterintuitive let alone paradoxical. For it doesn't matter how many 0's there are, $0+0+0+0\dots$ still should never add up to any number other than 0! Now this leads us to another fork in the road. Division by 0 can either be disallowed forever in arithmetic, OR an intuition could be established to allow it. Since intuitively there should be no difference between division by 0 and any other real number, it is simply "strange" to select the first option and simply disallow division by 0 as has been done in contemporary arithmetic. However, isn't it just as "strange" to select the second? How can there be an intuition to any amount of zeroes equalling anything but 0?

Eliminating the Pitfalls:

What if arithmetic doctrines have failed us in this manner; for what if there actually is an intuition behind $0*(1/0) = 1$ that we are failing to see through the clouds of our learned biases? What if 0 really is no different from any other number in that it could be divided? What if such paradoxes that arise actually are paradoxes that "make sense" and expose a larger truth?

*Establishing an Intuition for $0 * (1/0) = 1$ using Massimo Melli's Physical Zero*

In order to establish an intuition for any number of 0's equalling 1, the ontology of 0 vs. all other numbers needs to be re-established. Since numbers are a measure of components or size and 0 indicates a lack of components and size, then perhaps 0 should technically be different from all

other numbers, right? Well perhaps there is another manner to thinking about this. Per the “Logon Theory” of Massimo Melli, though 0 does indicate a lack of size, it still constitutes a physical existence. For such a “Physical Zero” would essentially need to underlie not just the number 1 but all numbers as a 0 dimensional coordinate. An example of this could be seen when trying to figure out the amount of numbers that lie between 3.2 and 3.3. For between 3.2 and 3.3 are clearly an infinite amount of numbers since more .01’s can always be added behind the decimal (10^{-X} ’s). However what would each of these infinite numbers between 3.2 and 3.3 then be? Would they constitute infinitesimal non-zero numbers? What would $(3.2-3.3)/\infty$ and therefore $.01/\infty$ equal? Well theoretically, such infinitesimal numbers would never actually be infinitesimal since there is nothing that stops more 10^{-X} ’s or .01’s from being added behind the decimal of said infinitesimal number. Since such a number would therefore tend towards 0, we could say that there are an infinite numbers of “physical zero dimensional points” situated between 3.2 and 3.3. Therefore $.01/\infty$ would equal 0 thus implying that $0 * \text{infinity} = .01$.

Since every number would essentially need to be composed of such infinitesimal 0 dimensional coordinates then it makes sense that it would take an infinite amount of such 0’s to make up a real number. The only thing however then that doesn’t make sense is how an infinite amount of such numbers ever actually equals a value different from any other value. Another means of demonstrating this paradox can be seen by the famous thought experiment “Zeno’s Arrow”.

Zeno’s Arrow

Zeno’s Arrow imagines an arrow being fired from a bow onto a certain “end” and asks the question of how to determine such an arrow’s properties at each point in space between the bow and the end. Well in order to determine the arrow’s properties at each point in space, it needs to be assumed that for each point in space the velocity of an arrow is 0. This is because if one were to precisely photograph each point in an arrow’s journey from the bow to the end with no period between photographs, then no photographs would show a “moving arrow”. Instead the arrow would always need to be at rest in each photograph (as a photograph could never show a moving image). However, if the arrow was at rest in each photograph how does it ever get to any end such as the other side of a field? Wouldn’t it always just stay still? For if it has a velocity of 0 at each point in time, then how can it ever establish itself the change in distance required to reach the “other side of the field”? For no matter how many moments there are in which the arrow travels, each moment would essentially constitute a velocity of 0 for the arrow! Therefore, even if there were an infinite amount of moments or “photographs”, shouldn’t the arrow still always have 0 velocity overall and never hit the wall!? Well sure, if at every moment the arrow has 0 velocity then it should never hit the wall. The only problem is that the arrow does hit the wall.

This shows how an infinite amount of “moments” each consisting of size “0” velocities can actually equal a distance travelled. Zeno’s arrow is essentially a classical example of the equation: $0 * (1/0) = X$ since an infinite amount of static moments with no velocity essentially equal a real amount of distance travelled. For if $\text{Distance} = \text{Speed} * \text{Time}$, then an infinite amount of moments each with 0 velocity essentially equals to X distance travelled.

This shows that even though such an idea is counterintuitive, since every number would need to be made up of an infinite amount of static 0 dimensional points (physical 0’s), an infinite amount

of 0's actually could still constitute a non-zero number. Zeno's arrow essentially shows that no matter the distance traveled, the path of the arrow still would need to be only made up of an infinite amount of 0 velocity moments. Therefore, whether the arrow travelled 1 foot or 1000 feet, the velocity = distance / time metric for the arrow would essentially still be the same. For X distance (10 or 1000 feet) is being travelled over an infinite amount of moments where the arrow travels at a velocity of 0 distance per moment. ($V = d/t$; $0 = X/(1/0) = (1/0 * 0 = x)$).

*Does this mean that $0 * (1/0) = X$ is intuitive?*

So now using this logic can it be concluded that $0 * \text{infinity}$ can in fact equal 1? If in fact there are an infinite number of 0's between 2.3 and 2.4 yet the distance between 2.3 and 2.4 still exists as .01 then this shows that $(x/0 * 0) = 1$ should hold true. Furthermore, if there are an infinite number of 0 velocity moments from when an arrow leaves the bow to when it hits an end yet the distance traveled still exists as a positive number then can't it be concluded that $0 * \text{infinity} = 1$ is intuitive!?

Well the issue that remains is that of " ∞ ". If there are an infinite amount of moments in the arrows path to the bow yet the arrows path to the bow only takes 10 minutes, then how could 10 minutes equal an infinite amount of moments? Shouldn't an infinite amount of minutes which of course is larger than 10 minutes equal an infinite amount of moments? Furthermore, if there are infinite amount of points between 3.2 and 3.3, then how could there similarly only be an infinite amount of points between 3.2 and 3.4 or 3.2 and infinity? Shouldn't the distance from 3.4 to infinity be larger than that of the distance from 3.2 to 3.3?

Furthermore, while Zeno's arrow can prove that $0 * \text{infinity} = 10$ feet it can also be proved that a velocity of 1 foot per minute * 10 minutes = 10 feet (which of course is intuitive). This is what is known as "Zeno's Paradox". Obviously if such a paradox is present then $0 * \text{infinity} = X$ can't be intuitive, right? For even if it makes sense that an infinite amount of infinitesimal physical zero's can add up to any number other than 0, it still doesn't make sense as to why an infinite amount of infinitesimal zero's can also add up to 1, 2 and 3 with 1 still equalling a value less than 2 and 2 still equalling a value less than 3. For if there is only one infinity that acts as the highest possible quantity in existence then all quantities being composed of essentially physical 0 "coordinates" wouldn't make any sense as such an amalgamation would always need to equal the highest number! For how can it not? What extra "0's" can be added to a quantity of 1 to make it a quantity of 2 if 1 already contains an infinite amount of 0's!?

A Final Answer

Now we have reached a final crossroad. Either we can give up the idea of finding a multiplicative inverse for 0 altogether and conclude that division by zero should not be allowed as it leads to paradoxes or however choose to accept said paradoxes and find a way that they actually make sense and "should" exist.

Since we are relentless in our search for a multiplicative inverse of 0 and refuse to give up and accept the arithmetic axiom of "division by zero being disallowed" we will select the latter.

Note that there is a fundamental problem with simply disallowing division by 0 in arithmetic. For arithmetic as a whole is essentially an epistemological system that is used to govern quantitative operations such as addition and multiplication. Since division is simply the reverse of multiplication and multiplication by 0 is allowed in arithmetic, there should be no reason that division by 0 is not. However, since division by 0 has been unable to have been worked out in a consistent manner thus far, a rule has been established that it is not allowed. In physics there is a similar issue with general relativity's equations seemingly not perfectly coinciding with what is observed. Like in arithmetic, current general relativity formulas seem to work perfectly in many cases yet completely fail in certain instances such as at the singularity of a black hole. In physics however it is not generally said that "black hole singularities cannot exist" because relativity formulas fail when they're involved. Rather it is acknowledged that general relativity needs to be modified to "fit" the phenomena of gravitational changes within black holes. Similarly, instead of disallowing division by 0 due to supposed paradoxes that come up, perhaps arithmetic needs to be modified to include division by 0 in a sensible consistent manner that complements such paradoxes.

Perhaps, explaining the paradoxes that come along with "division by 0" can be best accomplished through analyzing what was described earlier as the first pitfall of division by zero: the unintuitive equality of $0/0 = 1$. For if division by 0 is allowed and the multiplicative inverse of 0 is $1/0$ then:

$$0 * (1/0) = 1$$

$$(0/1) * (1/0) = 1 \text{ (since 0 is always equal to } 0/1)$$

$$0/0 = 1$$

This would seem to indicate that $0/0 = 1$. However, as previously stated - intuitively does $0/0$ make sense? How can 0 piles of 0 ever equal anything other than 0? For if 0 was divided into "0" piles then 0 would never be divided into any piles at all which essentially just means that a quantity of 0 should remain, right?

The intuition behind 0/0

Intuitively 0 piles of 0 should not simply mean a lack of quantity, but rather a lack of context. To explain, arithmetic is contextual by its very nature. When one adds 2 to 3 they are not "objectively" adding a quantity of 2 to a quantity of 3. For objectively there is no 2 or 3! Objectively, there is only infinity since infinity is the only thing that exists when there are no separations within itself. For if the universe is a whole infinite block with separations within it, then without separations it would simply be a whole block with no "notion" of components and therefore no quantities such as 2 or 3. Only when there are separations in this infinity, are contexts created in which "components" of this infinity could be separated out. These components of infinity are divided into "pockets of quantity" or "contexts" which is what allows them to be non-infinite numbers. Therefore, arithmetic is essentially subjective and contextual .

Furthermore, since arithmetic is essentially contextual by its very nature, then if there are "0" piles of any non-zero quantity, then the "context" of said quantity is completely removed - leaving only the unseparated infinity. The reason for this is that the "quantity" that exists within an arithmetic context exits the "confines" of the context when it divided by 0. For example,

imagine the infinite whole as a lattice of infinite components. Say that 5 of the infinite whole's components are then cut out from within the infinite whole at one time. This essentially creates a context of $5/1$ as 5 components are being divided into 1 pile separate from the infinite whole. However, what if one now wanted to cut 5 components out of the infinite whole 0 times? Essentially, this means that they would never cut the 5 components out of the infinite whole at all. It can also be demonstrated here how division is in fact the inverse of multiplication. If multiplying 5 by 0 in this case would cut "0" components out of the infinite whole 5 times, then dividing 5 by 0 would similarly be indicate the inverse of cutting 0 out of the infinite whole 5 times - cutting 5 out of the infinite whole 0 times. Cutting 5 out of the infinite whole 0 times of course just leaves the initial infinite whole - which by definition is infinity. For this reason any non-zero number divided by 0 equals infinity since any time there is a number being cut out of the infinite whole 0 times, there remains simply the infinite whole. However, what about 0? If 0 is a real quantity then shouldn't it also equals infinity when leaving its arithmetic context? Shouldn't cutting 0 out of the infinite whole 0 times simply leave the infinite whole which is infinity? (Such would imply that $0/0 = \infty!$).

Why wouldn't 0/0 be ∞ ?

There is essentially one unique property of 0 that renders is different from all other numbers - however it is not that it contains no multiplicative inverse. Rather it is simply that 0 is the floor of all absolute numbers. For there could never be any absolute quantity smaller than 0. As a proof for this, suppose that one were to divide 0 into any positive number of piles. What quantity would there then be in each pile? Of course there would still remain 0 quantity per pile as it doesn't matter the number of piles 0 is divided into, there should still only be 0 quantity to go around! It is this that is essentially "special" about 0. 0 is not special because it has no multiplicative inverse but rather because it never "needs" to be "inversely multiplied" at all. As inverse multiplication is simply division, this means that any quantity divided by 0 never *needs* to be divided out of the objective whole infinity in the first place and therefore remains infinity.

However, when it comes to $0/0$, not only does a number never need to be divided out of the infinity, but there is essentially no quantity that needs to exist either. Therefore, it is not so easy to suggest that infinity should be returned simply because there are 0 piles cut out of itself. Rather it is unclear in $0/0$ if infinity even "exists" since it is being suggested that there exists no quantity in no piles. After all, $0/0$ is essentially just $(x/0 \text{ which tends to infinity}) * 0!$ This implies that $0/0$ is the same as ∞ being instantiated 0 times. For if there are no instantiations of ∞ then how can $0/0$ ever be infinity!? However, as stated earlier if no piles automatically indicate the presence of infinity (since that which has no separations is only infinity), then how can this even make sense?

Perhaps this can best be explained through the example of an infinite cake:

The Infinite Cake

Imagine a bakery where only one cake is served. Since this cake automatically regenerates itself each time any sized piece is cut out of it, it is known as the "infinite cake". Furthermore, this bakery only has 3 rules:

1). Every order needs to be placed in terms of only numbers. For every time an order is placed, the customer is only asked to provide 2 pieces of information - 1) the amount of cake they want in terms of a measure of "area" and 2) the amount of slices they want the quantity of cake they requested to be split into. Customers order their cake on an "ordering machine" in the bakery where the default option is always set to 0 areas of cake and 0 slices prior to a customer putting in an order. When the customer begins an order they put in their name and then the amount of cake they want and a number of slices. Once the workers in the bakery see that a specific area or slice of cake is requested, they quickly know to begin preparing the order.

2) The second rule of the bakery is that if the order is ambiguous the customer must always get at least "the area" of the cake that he or she requested (the bakery wants no negative reviews).

3) Finally the third rule is that for each slice of cake the customer gets they always get a plate to go along with it.

Now for every order, there is a man whose job it is to take a knife and cut out an "area X" of cake among "Y" different slices and then provide Y plates - 1 for each slice.

For example, if someone's order is "5/1" then the man must cut out 1 piece of cake with a size of "area 5" on 1 plate. Similarly if someone orders "3/5" then the man must cut out 5 pieces of cake that together total an area of 3. Sometimes people even go to the bakery and order an area 0 of cake just because they like the plates. These orders would simply be written as $0/x$ where x is the amount of plates that they want and 0 the area of cake. So far the bakery is running in tip top shape and there is never any ambiguity to any order.

Now what happens if someone orders $5/0$? The customer wants a 5 area sized cake yet also wants there to be 0 slices cut on 0 plates? In this case the man looks at the cake counts a piece of area 5 and then thinks to himself "Wait, I can't cut an area 5 piece out of this cake in any way since the customer also wants there to be 0 slices of cake and no plates!". Therefore in order to ensure that the customer at least gets a "5 sized area" of cake (since rule 2 needs to be satisfied) the man simply takes the entire infinite cake and provides it to the customer.

However, what happens if someone orders $0/0$ pieces of cake? Easy, the order is never registered. It is as if the customer in question never ordered. Only once an area of cake or a number of slices more than 0 is specified does the bakery know to process the order. Therefore, it could be said that an order of $0/0$ simply means the customer in question hasn't ordered. They could eventually get a size "5 area" of cake cut into 3 slices, or maybe even the entire cake. Their order is therefore indeterminate and can eventually consist of any possible slices or area of cake. However, when the customer eventually does order, at that point the amount of cake they receive becomes real and their order could never again revert to $0/0$. Therefore, if one customer "Bob" has 2 slices of area 3 cake and another customer "John" has 2 slices of area 4 cake, it cannot be said that since at one point both their orders were $0/0$ that now Bob's total area 6 of cake is the same as John's area 8 of cake. For since both their orders processed they now each have determinate quantities of cake. Sure, the original $0/0$ order of cake for Bob became $6/2$

and for John became $8/2$, yet once the orders were processed they can no longer be set equal to one another as they are no longer $0/0$ but now $8/2$ and $6/2$.

Making Sense of the Infinite Cake

While the infinite cake may seem like a strange thought experiment, it actually does at least shine light on some confusing properties of arithmetic. Just like there is an “infinite cake” there is essentially also an infinite whole that exists as a “reserve of all possible quantity” to be utilized in arithmetic operations. Every time a number is put into context it is essentially being “cut out” of said infinite whole just as an area is cut out of the infinite cake. If the number is a whole number such as 5 then perhaps a quantity of 5 is separated from the infinite whole in one segment. If the number is $3/5$ then perhaps 3 components are separated from the infinite whole across 5 segments. If the number is 0 then a lack of quantity is separated from the infinite whole. How can 0 quantity be separated within the infinite whole? Easy, a 0 dimensional coordinate can simply be defined. A 0 dimensional coordinate would not have any size yet still “exist” as a physical zero. Furthermore, if the number is $x/0$ where $x > 0$ then x components could exist unseparated from the infinite whole which simply then essentially just leaves the entire infinite whole since if no segments were “cut” out of it then the entire infinite whole exists. Finally if $0/0$ is the number then it is as if the number in question is not even a number yet. It is simply any possible number. Only once the $0/0$ is defined as a number can it no longer constitute $0/0$ and thereby not be set equal to any other value.

*Another means to think about $0/0$ not tending towards infinity as do other numbers when divided by 0, is to see that $0/0$ is essentially the same as $0 * (x/0)$. Since $(x/0)$ defines infinity, $0/0$ essentially implies “not infinity” or 0 infinities. Infinity * 0 therefore does not denote the most infinitesimal component of any quantity within a context (that would be 0). It rather signifies the most infinitesimal “portion” of infinity. Furthermore, as infinity can never be defined by its components, $0/0$ would simply need to indicate “any possible future contextualization” of infinity, which of course could take on any quantity. Is it this definition of $0/0$ that essentially makes sense - a potential contextualization within infinity.*

Back to the Multiplicative Inverse of 0

Using this logic, can the multiplicative inverse of 0 finally be made sense of as $(1/0)$?

Well again if $1/0$ is the multiplicative inverse of 0, then:

$$0 * (1/0) = 1$$

Which is the same as:

$$0/0 = 1$$

Now it was also suggested that such an equation resulted in paradoxes; After all if it took an infinite amount of 0's to get a quantity of 1, then shouldn't it also take an infinite amount of 0's to get a quantity of 2?

Furthermore, there was also the original paradox that showed that if 0 does have a multiplicative inverse than it would immediately lead to a paradox since any number multiplied by 0 would have to equal 0:

So if $X * 0 = 0$

And $(1/0)$ is the multiplicative inverse of zero such that $(1/0) * 0 = 1$

then:

$(1/0) * 0 = 0$ which essentially just means that $0/0 = 0$

And

$(1*0) * 0 = 1$ which essentially just means that $0/0 = 1$

Is there finally a way to resolve such paradoxes? How can $0/0$ equal both 0, 1, 2 and every number at the same time?

The unique properties of 0/0

The answer is that perhaps $0/0$ has unique properties. For since $0/0$ is not a real number no one ever claimed that it needs to act “real” and “non-unique”. Rather, perhaps the true ontology of $0/0$ is not that it equals ever number but that it **can** equal any number. However, the point at which $0/0$ is definitely identified as a specific number, would also be the point at which it can never then equal any other number.

Take the example of flipping a coin. Prior to flipping said coin, it is unknown if the coin will eventually result in a heads or tails orientation. However once the coin is flipped as heads it could no longer be claimed to be “tails” as well. Such an example could be similar to how $0/0$ functions in arithmetic. Before any “number” or quantity is cut out of the infinite whole there is only the infinite whole that has “potential” components within it. However, once a “cut” is made in the infinite whole, a context is created and the quantities in that context are confined and limited to only their values.

Prior to the “cut” in the infinite whole, it can therefore be said that any possible quantity could arise. Such an “indeterminate” quantity can therefore be described by $0/0$. While 0 would act as the most infinitesimal number of “components” that could exist in a context once said context is separated from the infinite whole, $0/0$ would act differently. For $0/0$ would act as the most infinitesimal “portion” of that not yet cut from the infinite whole! In this way, while 0 would act as the “atom” or “logon” of any finite number of components within a context, $0/0$ would act as the “atom” of infinity. It would therefore be *indeterminate* in its quantity and only exist as the potential to “collapse” into any number.

However, once such indeterminacy has collapsed into a definitive value, that value is a real value and can no longer return to being described by $0/0$. Now perhaps at this point, it could be asked

- well why then would $0/0$ ever be equal to any number? If it only exists as “the potential” for any number then surely that is not the same as it simultaneously being every number at once!

Classically, yes it shouldn't be. However, the notion of superposition in quantum mechanics shows that prior to any system being definitively measured, the system simply exists in a state of all possible values at once. For in quantum mechanics, it is not simply that the system is *indeterminate* prior to measurement but rather superimposed as every possible potential state at once. In this way, it can be shown that if there is something that exists that has the potential to be anything, then it actually is “everything” until it is defined as only a singular “anything”.

In this way arithmetic can be modified. For instead of labeling $0/0$ as “indeterminate”, $0/0$ should rather be labeled as “superimposed” since such a definition is more in line with the somewhat counterintuitive standing of physical reality. Therefore, when $0/0$ introduces paradoxes and seems to equal both 0,1,2 and every real number at once it's not surprising. For it is actually perfectly in line with how reality works!

Furthermore, no paradoxes are actually introduced by division by zero therefore since every paradox that arises by division by 0 is ultimately reduced to $0/0 = \text{both } x \text{ and } y \text{ so } x \text{ must } = y$. However, if $0/0$ is like a physical superposition then it must not merely be indeterminate but actually equal every number at once while never allowing such numbers to ever equal one another. Since once $0/0$ is put into context as a specific number, like a superposition it has collapsed only into the value of that number.

(Note that it was first logician Walter Gomide who suggested superposition as the ontological nature of $0/0$).

Therefore if:

$$0 * (1/0) = 0$$
$$0/0 = 0$$

And:

$$0 * (1/0) = 1$$
$$0/0 = 1$$

And

$$0 * (2/0) = 2$$
$$0/0 = 2$$

No paradoxes actually exist! For it makes sense that $0/0$ is 0,1 and 2 at the same time. However, it also makes sense that once it is established as any single one of those numbers, then it could not be set equal to any other number since its value has definitively been identified!

Addressing the Final Pitfall and Grandi's Series

Note that while the paradoxes that come along with the multiplicative inverse of 0 have been explained along with the nature of $0/0$, there still perhaps exists the pitfall of the intuition of $0 \times \text{infinity}$ being set equal to any number other than 0. For wouldn't 0 apples placed into a bin an infinite number of times still result in a bin with 0 apples!? Perhaps not and such an intuition could be gained in this sense by the use of "Grandi's Series". "Grandi's Series" is described as an infinite series of $-1+1$ as being continued an infinite amount of times. Per the properties of an infinite series, it should not matter how such numbers are aligned. Therefore, such a series can also be described by $1 + (-1 + 1) + (-1 + 1) + (-1 + 1) + \dots = 1 + 0 + 0 + 0 + \dots = 1$. This ultimately shows how an infinite amount of 0's can actually intuitively equal to 1. Furthermore, another series arranged as $(1+1+1) + (-1+-1+-1)$ could similarly equal to $1+ 1 +1 + ((1+1+1) + (-1+-1+-1)) + ((1+1+1) + (-1+-1+-1)) + ((1+1+1) + (-1+-1+-1)) + \dots = 3 + 0 + 0 + 0 + \dots = 3$. Since both $-1+1$ and $((1+1+1) + (-1+-1+-1))$ are essentially both equal to 0, these series could similarly be described as the instantiation of $(0+0)$ an infinite amount of times (which of course is what resulted in paradoxes in the first place). It can therefore now be shown how $0 \times \text{infinity}$ could actually be equal any number. For the difference between $0 \times \text{infinity}$ equalling 1 and $0 \times \text{infinity}$ equalling 2 is not a question of "the number of infinities or inequality of one infinity to other infinities" it is rather an issue of the "perspective" from which such an infinite series is viewed. It is an issue of the **context** of the infinite series. In this way an intuition behind arithmetically adding an infinite amount 0's together in order to form any possible number could be built.

Future Articles

Future articles will elaborate on the concept of $0/0$ as superposition and also address how further arithmetic concepts can be explained to account for other physical phenomena. Additionally, while the example of an *infinite cake* has been explained, the example of an *infinite pie* (or *infinite pi*) will also be introduced.